

Nonlinear Dynamics

A novel infectious disease model verified by the case study of COVID-19 Pandemic --Manuscript Draft--

Manuscript Number:									
Full Title:	A novel infectious disease model verified by the case study of COVID-19 Pandemic								
Article Type:	Original Research								
Keywords:	infectious disease model; genetic algorithm; least square method; H.I.T. model; Deep learning								
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Funding Information:	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>The National Science Foundation of China (71850013)</td> <td>Dr. Lingkun Chen</td> </tr> <tr> <td>The National Science Foundation of China (71774042)</td> <td>Dr. Lingkun Chen</td> </tr> <tr> <td>The National Science Foundation of China (71271069)</td> <td>Dr. Lingkun Chen</td> </tr> <tr> <td>The National Science Foundation of China (5207080242)</td> <td>Dr. Lingkun Chen</td> </tr> </table>	The National Science Foundation of China (71850013)	Dr. Lingkun Chen	The National Science Foundation of China (71774042)	Dr. Lingkun Chen	The National Science Foundation of China (71271069)	Dr. Lingkun Chen	The National Science Foundation of China (5207080242)	Dr. Lingkun Chen
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A novel infectious disease model verified by the case study of COVID-19 Pandemic

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Abstract

In the background of the global epidemic of novel coronavirus (COVID-19)-infected pneumonia (NCIP). The present study first proposed a novel improved model of contagious diseases to predict contagious diseases in the early stage of the outbreak. Based on the S.I.R.S. (susceptible, infectious and removed, removed can turn susceptible again at limited immunity periods) model, the genetic algorithm and least square method optimize the parameters of infection rate, cure rate, and isolation rate. Finally, a new model is achieved-H.I.T. (Harbin Institute of Technology) model: The logarithm of the infection rate, cure rate, and reinfection rate of the model is calculated as more straight lines affected by the epidemic situation. then the general S.I.R.S. model and the available S.E.I.R. (susceptible, exposed, infectious and removed) model reflecting the effect of isolation measures base on genetic algorithm and least square method to optimize. Because each straight line can be regarded as neurons, the infection rate and cure rate parameters of each line is regarded as the weight of each layer, so the H.I.T. model also considered 7 traditional Deep learning algorithms-including formulas derivation and algorithms verification at SEIR model and SIR model. Because of the research about connection between the parameters of infection rate, cure rate and policy

such as lockdown and isolation, this study can provide technical support for the rapid response of urban public health emergencies.

Keywords: infectious disease model; genetic algorithm; least square method; H.I.T. model; Deep learning

Introduction

In December 2019, a novel coronavirus-infected pneumonia (NCIP) broke out in Wuhan, Hubei¹⁻², which was officially named as "2019 novel coronavirus" (COVID-19) on January 12, 2020. On March 11, 2020, the World Health Organization defined COVID-19 as a pandemic³⁻⁴. As of March 24, 2020, worldwide, more than a million people have been infected with the coronavirus in 2 weeks⁵. There are 1014137 confirmed cases, 199460 cured cases, 52948 dead cases, and 135 affected countries⁶.

The purpose of infectious disease dynamics is to establish a mathematical model according to human beings' physiological characteristic, human beings' physiological characteristics or other organisms to study the occurrence, transmission, and development of infectious diseases in a population by theoretical research and numerical simulation. Among all kinds of infectious disease models, the development of the compartment model is particularly noteworthy. The compartment model of contagious diseases originated from the study of Kermack and McKendrick in 1927. Based on London's black death cases from 1665 to 1666 and the plague cases in Bombay in 1906, they set up a susceptible infectious removed (S.I.R.) model. They created a dynamic method for the study of infectious diseases. This model was also called the ".M.K.M. model." In the .M.K.M. model, the total population is divided into three categories: susceptible, infectious (i.e., patients), cured and removed. On this basis, Kermack, McKendrick, and other researchers have proposed various infectious disease models, such as Susceptible-infectious (S.I.), Susceptible-infectious-Susceptible

(S.I.S.), Susceptible-infectious-removed-Susceptible (S.I.R.S.), Susceptible-exposed-infectious (S.E.I.), and Susceptible-exposed-infectious-removed (S.E.I.R.) models⁷⁻⁸.

Among them, the SEIR model is particularly worthy of attention due to considering the latent period of infectious diseases. In reality, there is usually a period between a person being infected and becoming an infection source, which is called the incubation period. SEIR model divides the population in the epidemic area into four categories: susceptible, latent, infectious, and cured. The model employs different equations to describe the transformation among these four groups of people.

In terms of disease types, the above models are generally applicable to the study of general laws of various infectious diseases. A few mathematical models are relevant to some exceptional cases. For example, Wanget al.⁹ and Tripathi et al.¹⁰ for AIDS, Zhou et al.¹¹ and Zhang et al.¹² for atypical pneumonia, and Elmojtaba et al.¹³ for leishmaniasis.

On the other hand, most of these models are suitable for the study of general contact transmission. In the model, the number of people infected and contacted by an infectious person in a unit time is affected by the total population and effective exposure rate of the area. Besides, some unique modes of communication were also discussed, i.g., the vertical transmission pathway¹⁴ and the isolation of patients¹⁵⁻¹⁶ were examined in these modes. In particular, the incidence of non-linear diseases has also been found¹⁷⁻¹⁸.

Recently, based on the data of 2014-2019 in the United States, Kissler et al.¹⁹ used the SEIRS model to describe the propagation dynamics of HCoV-OC43 and HCoV-HKU1. It is predicted that novel coronavirus pneumonia may become a seasonal threat, and viruses will repeatedly erupt in the winter after the outbreak of a pandemic. As was Caitlin M. Rivers said, an assistant professor of epidemiology at the Johns Hopkins

Center for Health Security, the NCIP will stay with us through 2022 that it's not going to die down to anything in the summer. It helps think what an intermittent "social distancing (More euphemistically, physical distancing)" policy is sustainable and effective²⁰ for reducing infectious disease.

By considering the incubation period and the quarantine state, Liu et al.²¹ developed an improved SEIQR model with distributed time delays and time-varying parameters in the model for better understanding of disease dynamics as well as for planning purposes. Many studies on COVID-19 shown that not only infected individuals are infectious, but also people in the incubation period have the same infectivity as infected individuals. To incorporate the time-fractional order and the coupling effect between cities, Lu et al.²². established a SEIHDR epidemic model to study the future control of dynamic behavior of COVID-19 base on reproduction number $R_0 \leq 1$.

Based on the susceptible-infected (S.I.) populations model, the S-shaped logistic and generalized logistic functions are introduced to describe the outbreak of the COVID-19 among various countries—China, Italy, Germany, and the U.S.A²³.

SEIR model analysis of an epidemiological model of COVID-19 by genetic algorithm consider public behavior and government action, this work points to the value of nonlinear dynamic analysis in pandemic modeling and demonstrates the dramatic influence of social and government behavior on disease dynamics²⁴.

To analyze an epidemiological model, our work is quite similar to Weinan E, which both use deep neural networks SGD(stochastic gradient descent) method approximation of high dimensions cure rate, infection rate of partial differential equations, it is less sensitive to the dimensionality of the problem and has the potential

to work in rather high dimensions²⁵.

In a word, the research emphases of the above mathematical models are: (1) to establish a model to describe the law of disease diffusion; (2) to discuss the stability of the solution of the model, the persistence and periodicity of infectious diseases, and to solve the equilibrium point of endemic diseases and the first regeneration number of conditions. However, the intelligent optimization of the model's parameters has not been improved, and the genetic algorithm and extended Kalman filter have not been applied to the improvement of the infectious disease model. There is no specific research on the prediction of the early stage of sudden contagious diseases in large cities. Studies have shown that coronavirus infection begins to spread in small populations, and early recognition of these populations is essential to slow down the virus's spread²⁶. Thus, this work aims to look at the data available on the number of infections and analyze the infection dynamics development based on the SIRS and SEIR model. This present study uses a genetic algorithm, least square method and deep learning to optimize infection rate parameters, cure rate, infection rate parameters, cure rate, and isolation rate. It then verifies the infectious disease model parameters through extended Kalman filter tracking data. Finally, it achieves a better-improved model to make a more scientific prediction of the epidemic situation.

Model and methods

The research object of the SIRS infectious disease model is the early warning, prediction, and prevention and control of epidemic development in a specific area. The total number of people in each region are same with each other. The population is divided into three categories: susceptible, infected, and removed . The number of three kinds of people at time t is recorded as $s(t)$, $i(t)$ and $r(t)$. The daily infection rate of patients is λ , and the daily infection rate of each region is obtained by the finite

difference method or. The daily cure rate is μ , which is related to the medical treatment in each area and changes with the optimal allocation of medical resources in each region. After the recovery, only temporary immunity is available for the patients who have moved out. In a unit time, the patients who have moved out will lose protection and become infected again.

Remember that the proportion of susceptible, infected, and removed persons at the initial time is $s_0(s_0 > 0)$, $i_0(i_0 > 0)$ and $r_0(r_0 > 0)$, respectively. Then the equations of the SIRS model are as follows:

$$\frac{ds(t)}{dt} = -\lambda s(t)i(t) + \gamma r(t) \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{di(t)}{dt} = \lambda s(t)i(t) - \mu i(t) \quad (2)$$

$$\frac{dr(t)}{dt} = \mu i(t) - \gamma r(t) \quad (3)$$

$$s(t) + i(t) + r(t) = N \quad (4)$$

Formulas (1), (2), and (3) show the number of changes of susceptible, infected, and displaced persons, respectively. The number of vulnerable people will decrease when they become infected, and increase when the movers are transformed into new susceptible people; The number of infected people increase when they become infected, and decrease when some infected people are transformed into movers; the number of movers will increase when the infected people are transformed into movers, and increase when the movers can become susceptible again reduce. Formula (4) denotes the sum of the number of susceptible, infected, and displaced persons.

If only consider the patients' control, there are two methods generally used in medicine: one is to treat the patients with effective drugs; the other is to isolate the patients to avoid the contact between the patients and the susceptible. Letting k_1 and k_2 represent isolation rate and cure rate respectively, then consider the following forms of control period: $u = -k_1 \lambda s i(t) - k_2 i(t)$.

Figure 1 SEIR flow chart

SEIR infectious disease model, the research object is the early warning, prediction, and prevention and control of epidemic development in a particular area. The total number of people in each region is the same. The population is divided into four categories as susceptible, latent, infected, and displaced. At the time of t , the number of four kinds of people was recorded as, $s(t)$, $e(t)$, $i(t)$ and $r(t)$, respectively, and those who moved out included those who died and those who were cured, $h(t)$ and $l(t)$, respectively. The probability of the susceptible to be transformed into the latent is λ_1 , and the probability of the susceptible to be transformed into the latent is λ_2 . The probability of the latent being transformed into the infected is α , the probability of the infected being transformed into the cured is μ , and the likelihood of the infected being transformed into the dead is δ . Remember that the proportion of susceptible, infected, and removed persons at the initial time is $s_0(s_0 > 0)$, $e_0(e_0 > 0)$, $i_0(i_0 > 0)$ and $h_0(h_0 > 0)$, respectively, The SEIR flow chart is shown in Figure 1. Then, the SEIR model equation can be written as follows:

$$\frac{ds(t)}{dt} = -\lambda_1 s(t)i(t) - \lambda_2 s(t)e(t) + \gamma h(t) \quad (5)$$

$$\frac{de(t)}{dt} = \lambda_1 s(t)i(t) + \lambda_2 s(t)e(t) - \alpha e(t) \quad (6)$$

$$\frac{di(t)}{dt} = \alpha e(t) - \mu i(t) - \delta l(t) \quad (7)$$

$$\frac{dh(t)}{dt} = \mu i(t) - \gamma h(t) \quad (8)$$

$$s(t) + e(t) + i(t) + r(t) = N \quad (9)$$

$$r(t) = h(t) + l(t) \quad (10)$$

where formulas (5), (6), (7), and (8) show the number of changes of susceptible, latent, infected, and cured people, respectively. First, the number of sensitive people will decrease because of the infected and latent people's infection. Secondly, The number of lurkers will increase because of the change from susceptible to latent, and decrease because of the shift to infected. The number of infected people will increase because of the shift in sensitive people to infected people and decrease because of the change in some infected people to cured and dead people. The number of healers increases as the infected become healers and decreases as the infected become susceptible again. Formula (9) is the sum of the number of sensitive, latent, infected, and displaced persons, and equation (10) is the sum of the number of displaced persons.

Algorithm

Worthy noted that, compared with the general SIRS model, which sets infection rate, isolation rate, and cure rate to solve the differential equation, the present study uses a genetic algorithm and least square method to obtain the infection rate, cure rate and isolation rate of the model, mainly to match the number of people infected and the number of people removed. The genetic algorithm was first proposed in 1975. Inspired by the theory of biological evolution, "survival of the fittest", an intelligent optimization algorithm with highly parallel and adaptive characteristics was proposed by researcher J.H. Holland. They claimed that the objective function of equation (11) - equation (13) is close to 0, they can be considered as follows:

$$\min \sum (\mu i(t) - \gamma r(t) - \text{diff } r(t))^2 \quad (11)$$

Find out μ and γ of formula (13) and then find λ of equation (14).

$$\min \sum (\lambda i(t) - \mu i(t) - \text{diff } i(t))^2 \quad (12)$$

For the case of considering isolation, the μ and γ of formula (5) are calculated, and then the λ and k of formula (15) are calculated. Since the initial $r(t)$ and $i(t)$ are much smaller than $s(t)$, so $s(t)$ can be regarded as 1. At the beginning of $ds(t)$ the controller $u = -k_1(t)\lambda(t)i(t) - k_2(t)i(t)$ can be simplified as $u = -k(t)i(t)$.

$$\min \sum (\lambda i(t) - \mu i(t) - \text{diff } i(t) - k(t)i(t))^2 \quad (13)$$

For the SEIRS model, the optimization equation is as follows, so that the objective functions of formula (13) and formula (16) are close to 0, and the μ and γ of formula (13) are calculated. Then the α of formula (14) is calculated.

$$\min \sum (\alpha e(t) - \mu i(t) - \delta l(t) - \text{diff } e(t))^2 \quad (14)$$

Whether SIRS model or SEIR model, it is assumed that the cure rate accords with the exponential increasing change, that is to say, it need to get the appropriate a and b , μ as follows, and less than 1, x is the time series of samples, x is 1 to n . The logarithm of cure rate μ is a line segment with slope $a > 0$. When a specific vaccine is developed, the cure rate will rise steeper at the inflection point and become a broken line.

$$\mu = \min(\exp(ax + b), 1) \quad (15)$$

For the infection rate for the infection rate, because the people did not know that there would be an outbreak at the time of the epidemic, because the increase of the number of infected people started to increase exponentially, and then measures such as closing the city would cause the infection rate to change exponentially again, so there are two infection rate formulas (16) and (17). The SEIR model that only provides suspected data can not fully reflect the lurk, so α should be greater than 1, such as the constant c_1 of α range. The logarithm of the infection rate

λ_1 is the first segment of the broken line, and λ_2 is the second segment of the broken line; the logarithm of the suspected conversion rate α_1 is the first segment of the broken

line, and α_2 is the second segment of the broken line.

In addition to the parameter of formula (16), a sequence parameter is also needed, which is the label i from decreasing to increasing inflection point. The coordinates $(i, ci+d)$ also conform to $y=ex+f$. substituting $ei+f=ci+d$, i.e., $f=(c-e)i+d$, i.e., formula (17) and (19) are modified to formula (20) and (21), i.e., four parameters of c 、 d 、 e 和 I need to be fitted, and an optimal parameter range c_1 needs to be fitted for SEIR model.

We call formula (15) - (21) the HIT model.

$$\lambda_1 = \min(\exp(cx + d), 1) \quad (16)$$

$$\lambda_2 = \min(\exp(ex + f), 1) \quad (17)$$

$$\alpha_1 = \min(\exp(cx + d), c_1) \quad (18)$$

$$\alpha_2 = \min(\exp(ex + f), c_1) \quad (19)$$

$$\lambda_2 = \min(\exp(ex + (c - e)i + d), 1) \quad (20)$$

$$\alpha_2 = \min(\exp(ex + (c - e)i + d), c_1) \quad (21)$$

The probability of reinfection and misdiagnosis is small. $\exp(g)$ ranges from 0-0.02, i.e. the upper limit of g is $\log(0.02)=-3.9120$. After taking the logarithm, first, there is a parallel line, then there is a decrease in the inflection Mark j , i.e. $(j, hj-g)$, i.e., three parameters of g , h and j need to be fitted

$$\gamma_1 = \exp(g) \quad (21)$$

$$\gamma_2 = \exp(h(x - j)-g) \quad (22)$$

Case study

The number of iterations of the genetic algorithm is 1500, and the population size is 1500 in this paper, Wuhan and Jilin epidemic data as an example to verify the models feasibility. And compare Wuhan's data with that of Changsha to change the infection

rate of Wuhan data and make it closer to the epidemic data of Changsha. The data of Wuhan and Jilin is shown in Appendix A1 and A2.

The SIRS model was used to simulate the epidemic situation in Wuhan, and the SERIS model was used to affect the epidemic situation in Jilin.

It is assumed that Wuhan has a population of 9 million, and Jilin has 27 million. Normalized $R(t)$, $S(t)$ and $I(t)$ to 0-1 for 0-9 million and 27 million respectively.

Case study of epidemic data in Jilin province

Based on the SEIR model, because there are still healthy people in the suspected patients, and the alleged patients do not include asymptomatic virus carriers, so the apparent patients can not be regarded as the latent ones, the suspected conversion rate α range should be greater than 3.25 out of 1, followed by $R(T)$ actual and fitting correlation 0.9984, $I(T)$ real and fit correlation 0.9686, cure rate $\mu(T)$ The logarithm of ceil $(4.6988 / 0.0778) = 61$ days after the closure of the city, the logarithm of the suspected conversion rate $\alpha(T)$ first decreased slowly, $y = -0.0349x - 2.4850$ isolation effect, then declined steeply $y = -0.3320(X-9) - 0.0349 * 9 - 2.4850$, the inflection point $(9, -0.0349 * 9 - 2.4850)$, and the rate of reinfection was not considered. The dynamics simulation of the Jilin SEIR model is shown in Figure 2. As can be seen in Figure 2, the actual results are in good agreement with the dynamic modeling results. $c_1=7.1646$.

Analysis of Girin cases

Figure 2. Dynamics simulation of Jilin SEIR model

Case study of epidemic data in Wuhan

If Kriging interpolation correction is considered, Kriging interpolation is considered for data from February 7 to February 11. The simulation of the Wuhan dynamics model modified by interpolation is shown in Figure 3 and Figure 4. Figure 3 shows the decrease of infection rate in SIRS dynamic simulation in Wuhan: The decrease of

infection rate is as follows: decrease of infection rate: the correlation between the actual and fitting data of $r(t)$ is 0.9952, the correlation between the actual and fitting data of the number of confirmed patients is 0.9981, and the logarithm of cure rate $\mu(t)$ is linearly increasing $y = 0.0882 X - 5.8967$. If the specific vaccine is launched, the cure rate's logarithm should be a broken line that increases slowly and then steeply, and the upper limit of the cure rate should be calculated ($y = 0$). After $\text{ceil}(5.8967 / 0.0882) = 67$ days, the logarithm of the infection rate $\lambda(t)$ first decreases linearly by $y = -0.0434x - 0.8882$ and then decreases linearly by $y = -0.2074(x - 14) - 0.0434 * 14 - 0.8882$, the inflection point (14, $-0.0434 * 14 - 0.8882$), reinfection rate $y = 0.038$ and $y = -14.9831(X - 29) - 0.038$, inflection point (29, 0.038).

Figure 3.Reinfestation rate against with time in SIRS dynamic simulation in Wuhan

Figure 4 shows the increase of infection rate of SIRS dynamic simulation in Wuhan, and the sequence is as follows: the correlation between the actual and fitting data of $r(t)$ is 0.9929, the correlation between the actual and fitting data of the number of confirmed patients is 0.9898, and the logarithm of cure rate $\mu(t)$ is linearly increasing $y = 0.0822 X - 5.8967$. If the specific vaccine is launched, the logarithm of cure rate should be a broken line of slow and then step increase, and the upper limit of cure rate $\log(y = 0)$ should be calculated. After $\text{ceil}(5.8967 / 0.0882) = 70$ days, the logarithm of infection rate $\lambda(t)$ first decreases linearly $y = -0.1328x - 0.0223$ and then increases linearly $y = 0.9729 (X - 38) - 0.1328 * 38 - 0.022$, the inflection point $(38, -0.1328 * 38 - 0.022)$, reinfestation rate $y = 0.0481$ and $y = -4.1727 (X - 29) - 0.0481$, inflection point $(29, 0.0481)$. It can be seen from Figure 3 that the actual results are agree well with the dynamic modeling results.

Figure 4. Infection rate rise of SIRS dynamic simulation in Wuhan

Base on deep learning to obtain model-Formulas derivation and algorithms verification

Base on the SEIR model Formulas (5)-(10) to derivate, HIT model each straight line can be regarded as neurons, the infection rate and cure rate parameters of each line are regarded as the weight of each layer. The deep learning research of the SEIR model based on Jilin data introduces the activation function $\text{tansig}(\Delta y)$, so that the activation

function $\text{tansig}(\Delta y)$ of each generation of evacuees and diagnoses increases based on the gradient method to become $1-\Delta y^2$, Iterate 150,000 times, and check whether the current solution converges every 60 generations, otherwise replace it with the solution before 60 ages.

Because it is a multi-line model-that is, the time distribution of the cure rate and the infection rate is expressed as a multi-fold line, it is necessary to calculate the start and end values of the cure rate μ , and the infection rate λ of each polyline, which is determined by the $\mu(k)$ and $\lambda(k)$ Obtain the expression of the broken line segment and then iterate the gradient. The probability α of the suspect to be diagnosed is a fixed value, but every iteration of each infection rate calculation has broken line updates α .

j is the current iteration, j_{\max} is the maximum iteration, $(j_{\max}-j)/j_{\max}$ makes the coarse search first, and then the refined search.

In the B.G.D. algorithm, the cure rate μ , reinfection rate γ , and infection rate λ are updated as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta r(n_3(k):n_3(k)+n_1(k)-1) &= \left(i(n_3(k):n_3(k)+n_1(k)-1) + i(n_3(k)+1:n_3(k)+n_1(k)) \right) / 2.* \\ &\exp \left(\frac{(\log \mu(k+1) - \log \mu(k)) / (n_1(k)-1)(n_3(k):n_3(k)+n_1(k)-1)}{-(\log \mu(k+1) - \log \mu(k)) / (n_1(k)-1)n_3(k) + \log \mu(k)} \right) \\ \Delta i_2(n_3(k):n_3(k)+n_1(k)-1) &= \left(i(n_3(k):n_3(k)+n_1(k)-1) + i(n_3(k)+1:n_3(k)+n_1(k)) \right) / 2.* \\ &\exp \left(\frac{(\log \mu(k+1) - \log \mu(k)) / (n_1(k)-1)(n_3(k):n_3(k)+n_1(k)-1)}{-(\log \mu(k+1) - \log \mu(k)) / (n_1(k)-1)n_3(k) + \log \mu(k)} \right) \\ \Delta i_1(n_3(k):n_3(k)+n_1(k)-1) &= \alpha \left(e(n_3(k):n_3(k)+n_1(k)-1) + e(n_3(k)+1:n_3(k)+n_1(k)) \right) / 2.* \\ &\exp \left(\frac{(\log \lambda(k+1) - \log \lambda(k)) / (n_1(k)-1)(n_3(k):n_3(k)+n_1(k)-1)}{-(\log \lambda(k+1) - \log \lambda(k)) / (n_1(k)-1)n_3(k) + \log \lambda(k)} \right) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\Delta i(k) &= \Delta i_1(k) - \Delta i_2(k) \\
g_\mu(k) &= \sum_{n=n_3(k)-t_1}^{n_3(k)+n_1(k)-1+t_2} (-r(n) + h_r(n)) \cdot \Delta r(n-1) / 1E1(j \max - j) \\
&\quad * (1 - \Delta r(n-1)^2) \cdot (n-1-n_3(k)) / (n_1(k)-1) \\
g_\lambda(k) &= \sum_{n=n_3(k)-t_1}^{n_3(k)+n_1(k)-1+t_2} (-i(n) + h_i(n)) \cdot \Delta i(n-1) / 1E - 9(j \max - j) \\
&\quad * (1 - \Delta i(n-1)^2) \cdot (n-1-n_3(k)) / (n_1(k)-1) \\
g_\alpha &= \sum_{n=n_3(k)-t_1}^{n_3(k)+n_1(k)-1+t_2} (-i(n) + h_i(n)) \cdot \Delta i(n-1) / 1E - 9(j \max - j) \\
&\quad * (1 - \Delta i(n-1)^2) / \alpha \\
\mu(k) &= \mu(k) - g_\mu(k) \\
\lambda(k) &= \lambda(k) - g_\lambda(k) \\
\alpha &= \alpha - g_\alpha \\
(23)
\end{aligned}$$

in which, the data and fitting correlations of removers and confirmed patients were 0.9939 and 0.9855, respectively.

In the SGD algorithm, the update formulas for the cure rate μ , the reinfection rate γ and the infection rate λ are as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
g_\mu(k) &= (-r(n) + h_r(n)) \Delta r(n-1) / 1E1(j \max - j) \\
&\quad / j \max (1 - \Delta r(n-1)^2) (n-1-n_3(k)) / (n_1(k)-1) \\
g_\lambda(k) &= (-i(n) + h_i(n)) \Delta i(n-1) / 1E \\
&\quad - 9(j \max - j) / j \max (1 - \Delta i(n-1)^2) (n-1-n_3(k)) / (n_1(k)-1) \\
g_\alpha &= (-i(n) + h_i(n)) \Delta i(n-1) / 1E - 9(j \max - j) / j \max (1 - \Delta i(n-1)^2) / \alpha \\
\mu(k) &= \mu(k) - g_\mu(k) \\
\lambda(k) &= \lambda(k) - g_\lambda(k) \\
(24)
\end{aligned}$$

$\alpha = \alpha - g_\alpha$ in which, the data and fitting correlations of removers and confirmed patients were 0.9996 and 0.9972, respectively.

In the Momentum-SGD algorithm, the update formulas for the cure rate μ , the reinfection rate γ , and the infection rate λ are as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
m &= 0.1 \\
g_\mu(k) &= mg_\mu(k) \\
&\quad + (-r(n) + h_r(n))\Delta r(n-1)/1E1(j \max - j) \\
&\quad /j \max(1 - \Delta r(n-1)^2) (n-1-n3(k))/(n1(k)-1) \\
g_\lambda(k) &= mg_\lambda(k) + (-i(n) + h_i(n))\Delta i1(n-1)/1E \\
&\quad - 9(j \max - j)/j \max(1 - \Delta i(n-1)^2) (n-1-n3(k))/(n1(k)-1) \\
g_\alpha &= mg_\alpha + (-i(n) + h_i(n))\Delta i1(n-1)/1E \\
&\quad - 9(j \max - j)/j \max(1 - \Delta i(n-1)^2) / \alpha \\
\mu(k) &= \mu(k) - g_\mu(k) \\
\lambda(k) &= \lambda(k) - g_\lambda(k) \\
\alpha &= \alpha - g_\alpha \\
(25)
\end{aligned}$$

In which, data and fitting correlations of removers and confirmed patients are 0.9995 and 0.9975, respectively.

In the AdaGrad algorithm, the update formulas for the cure rate μ , the reinfection rate γ , and the infection rate λ are as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
g_\mu(k) &= (-r(n) + h_r(n))\Delta r(n-1)(1 - \Delta r(n-1)^2)(n-1-n3(k))/(n1(k)-1) \\
g_\lambda(k) &= (-i(n) + h_i(n))\Delta i1(n-1)(1 - \Delta i(n-1)^2)(n-1-n3(k))/(n1(k)-1) \\
g_\alpha &= (-i(n) + h_i(n))\Delta i1(n-1)(1 - \Delta i(n-1)^2)/\alpha \\
v(k)_\mu &= v(k)_\mu + g_\mu(k)^2 \\
v(k)_\lambda &= v(k)_\lambda + g_\lambda(k)^2 \\
v_\alpha &= v_\alpha + g_\alpha^2 \\
\mu(k) &= \mu(k) - g_\mu(k)/\sqrt{v(k)_\mu + 1e-10/1E-2(j \max - j)/j \max}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\lambda(k) = \lambda(k) - g_\lambda(k) / \sqrt{v(k)_\gamma + 1e-10} / 1E-4(j \max - j) / jmax$$

$$\alpha = \alpha - g_\alpha / \sqrt{v_\alpha + 1e-10} / 1E-4(j \max - j) / jmax$$

(26)

In which, the data and fitting correlations of removers and confirmed patients are 0.9962 and 0.9925, respectively.

In the AdaDelta algorithm, the update formulas for the cure rate μ , the reinfection rate γ and the infection rate λ are as follows:

$$m = 0.1$$

$$beta_1 = 0.999$$

$$g_\mu(k) = mg_\mu(k)$$

$$+ (-r(n) + h_r(n)) \Delta r(n-1) (1 - \Delta r(n-1)^2) (n-1-n3(k)) / (n1(k)-1)$$

$$g_\lambda(k) = mg_\lambda(k)$$

$$+ (-i(n) + h_i(n)) \Delta i(n-1) (1 - \Delta i(n-1)^2) (n-1-n3(k)) / (n1(k)-1)$$

$$g_\alpha = mg_\alpha + (-i(n) + h_i(n)) \Delta i(n-1) (1 - \Delta i(n-1)^2) / \alpha$$

$$v(k)_\mu = beta_1 v(k)_\mu + g_\mu(k)^2$$

$$v(k)_\lambda = beta_1 v(k)_\lambda + g_\lambda(k)^2$$

$$v_\alpha = beta_1 v_\alpha + g_\alpha^2$$

$$\mu(k) = \mu(k) - g_\mu(k) / \sqrt{v(k)_\mu + 1e-10} / 1E-1(j \max - j) / jmax$$

$$\lambda(k) = \lambda(k) - g_\lambda(k) / \sqrt{v(k)_\gamma + 1e-10} / 1E-4(j \max - j) / jmax$$

$$\alpha = \alpha - g_\alpha / \sqrt{v_\alpha + 1e-10} / 1E-4(j \max - j) / jmax$$

(27)

In which, the data and fitting correlations of removers and confirmed patients are 0.9958 and 0.9932, respectively.

In the Adax algorithm, the update formulas for the cure rate μ , the reinfection rate γ ,

and the infection rate λ are as follows:

$$m_\mu = 0.1$$

$$m_\lambda = 0.1$$

$$m_\alpha = 0.1$$

$$beta_1 = 0.9$$

$$beta_2 = 0.0001$$

$$g_\mu(k) = mg_\mu(k)$$

$$+ (-r(n) + h_r(n))\Delta r(n-1)(1 - \Delta r(n-1)^2)(n-1-n3(k))/(n1(k)-1)$$

$$g_\lambda(k) = mg_\lambda(k)$$

$$+ (-i(n) + h_i(n))\Delta i1(n-1)(1 - \Delta i(n-1)^2)(n-1-n3(k))/(n1(k)-1)$$

$$g_\alpha = mg_\alpha + (-i(n) + h_i(n))\Delta i1(n-1)(1 - \Delta i(n-1)^2)/\alpha$$

$$m_\mu = beta_1 m_\mu + (1 - beta_1)g_\mu(k)$$

$$m_\lambda = beta_1 m_\lambda + (1 - beta_1)g_\lambda(k)$$

$$m_\alpha = beta_1 m_\alpha + (1 - beta_1)g_\alpha(k)$$

$$v(k)_\mu = (1 + beta_2)v(k)_\mu + beta_2 g_\mu(k)^2$$

$$v(k)_\lambda = (1 + beta_2)v(k)_\lambda + beta_2 g_\lambda(k)^2$$

$$v_\alpha = (1 + beta_2)v_\alpha + beta_2 g_\alpha^2$$

$$vg(k)_\mu = v(k)_\mu / (1 + beta_2)^{j-1}$$

$$vg(k)_\lambda = v(k)_\lambda / (1 + beta_2)^{j-1}$$

$$vg_\alpha = v(k)_\alpha / (1 + beta_2)^{j-1}$$

$$\mu(k) = \mu(k) - m_\mu / \sqrt{vg(k)_\mu + 1e-10/1E9(j \max - j)/j \max}$$

$$\lambda(k) = \lambda(k) - m_\lambda / \sqrt{vg(k)_\lambda + 1e-10/1E10(j \max - j)/j \max}$$

$$\alpha = \alpha - m_\alpha / \sqrt{vg_\alpha + 1e-10/1E10(j \max - j)/j \max}$$

(28)

in which, the data and fitting correlations of removers and confirmed patients are 0.9825

and 0.8797, respectively.

In the Adam algorithm, the update formulas for the cure rate μ , the reinfection rate γ ,

and the infection rate λ are as follows:

$$m_\mu = 0.1$$

$$m_\lambda = 0.1$$

$$m_\alpha = 0.1$$

$$beta_1 = 0.9$$

$$beta_2 = 0.999$$

$$g_\mu(k) = mg_\mu(k)$$

$$+ (-r(n) + h_r(n))\Delta r(n-1)(1 - \Delta r(n-1)^2)(n-1-n3(k))/(n1(k)-1)$$

$$g_\lambda(k) = mg_\lambda(k)$$

$$+ (-i(n) + h_i(n))\Delta i(n-1)(1 - \Delta i(n-1)^2)(n-1-n3(k))/(n1(k)-1)$$

$$g_\alpha = mg_\alpha + (-i(n) + h_i(n))\Delta i(n-1)(1 - \Delta i(n-1)^2)/\alpha$$

$$m_\mu = beta_1 m_\mu + (1 - beta_1)g_\mu(k)$$

$$m_\lambda = beta_1 m_\lambda + (1 - beta_1)g_\lambda(k)$$

$$m_\alpha = beta_1 m_\alpha + (1 - beta_1)g_\alpha(k)$$

$$v(k)_\mu = beta_2 v(k)_\mu + (1 - beta_2)g_\mu(k)^2$$

$$v(k)_\lambda = beta_2 v(k)_\lambda + (1 - beta_2)g_\lambda(k)^2$$

$$v_\alpha = beta_2 v_\alpha + (1 - beta_2)g_\alpha^2$$

$$vg(k)_\mu = v(k)_\mu / (1 - beta_2^j)$$

$$vg(k)_\lambda = v(k)_\lambda / (1 - beta_2^j)$$

$$vg_\alpha = v_\alpha / (1 - beta_2^j)$$

$$mg(k)_\mu = m_\mu / (1 - beta_1^j)$$

$$mg(k)_\lambda = m_\lambda / (1 - beta_1^j)$$

$$mg_\alpha = m_\alpha / (1 - beta_1^j)$$

$$\mu(k) = \mu(k) - mg(k)_\mu / \sqrt{vg(k)_\mu + 1e-10/1E9(j \max - j)/j \max}$$

$$\lambda(k) = \lambda(k) - mg(k)_\lambda / \sqrt{vg(k)_\lambda + 1e-10} / 1E10(jmax - j) / jmax$$

$$\alpha = \alpha - mg_\alpha / \sqrt{vg_\alpha + 1e-10} / 1E10(jmax - j) / jmax$$

(29)

in which, the data and fitting correlations of removers and confirmed patients were 0.9778 and 0.9597, respectively.

Using the deep learning research method based on the S.I.R. model formulas (1)-(4) to derivate. Solving formulas requires 150,000 iterations, and check whether the current solution has converged after every 60 generations, otherwise replace it with the solution before 60 generations.

For the BGD algorithm, the cure rate, reinfection rate, and infection rate update formula are as follows: The data and fitting correlations of removers and confirmed patients are 0.9998 and 0.9973, respectively.

$$\Delta r(n3(k):n3(k)+n1(k)-1) = \left(i(n3(k):n3(k)+n1(k)-1) + i(n3(k)+1:n3(k)+n1(k)) \right) / 2.*$$

$$\exp \left(\begin{array}{l} (\log \mu(k+1) - \log \mu(k)) / (n1(k)-1)(n3(k):n3(k)+n1(k)-1) \\ - (\log \mu(k+1) - \log \mu(k)) / (n1(k)-1)n3(k) + \log \mu(k) \end{array} \right)$$

$$\Delta i_2(n3(k):n3(k)+n1(k)-1) = \left(i(n3(k):n3(k)+n1(k)-1) + i(n3(k)+1:n3(k)+n1(k)) \right) / 2.*$$

$$\exp \left(\begin{array}{l} (\log \mu(k+1) - \log \mu(k)) / (n1(k)-1)(n3(k):n3(k)+n1(k)-1) \\ - (\log \mu(k+1) - \log \mu(k)) / (n1(k)-1)n3(k) + \log \mu(k) \end{array} \right)$$

$$\Delta i_1(n3(k):n3(k)+n1(k)-1) = \left(i(n3(k):n3(k)+n1(k)-1) + i(n3(k)+1:n3(k)+n1(k)) \right) / 2.*$$

$$\exp \left(\begin{array}{l} (\log \lambda(k+1) - \log \lambda(k)) / (n1(k)-1)(n3(k):n3(k)+n1(k)-1) \\ - (\log \lambda(k+1) - \log \lambda(k)) / (n1(k)-1)n3(k) + \log \lambda(k) \end{array} \right)$$

$$\Delta i(k) = \Delta i_1(k) - \Delta i_2(k)$$

$$g_{\mu}(k) = \sum_{n=n_3(k)-t_1}^{n_3(k)+n_1(k)-1+t_2} (-r(n) + h_r(n)) \cdot \Delta r(n-1) / 1E2(j \max - j) / j \max. \\ * (1 - \Delta r(n-1)^2) \cdot (n-1-n_3(k)) / (n_1(k)-1)$$

$$g_{\lambda}(k) = \sum_{n=n_3(k)-t_1}^{n_3(k)+n_1(k)-1+t_2} (-i(n) + h_i(n)) \cdot \Delta i(n-1) / 1E - 2(j \max - j) / j \max. \\ * (1 - \Delta i(n-1)^2) \cdot (n-1-n_3(k)) / (n_1(k)-1)$$

$$\mu(k) = \mu(k) - g_{\mu}(k) \\ \lambda(k) = \lambda(k) - g_{\lambda}(k) \\ (30)$$

For the SGD algorithm, the cure rate, reinfection rate, and infection rate update formula are as follows:

$$g_{\mu}(k) = (-r(n) + h_r(n)) \Delta r(n-1) / 1E1(j \max - j) \\ / j \max (1 - \Delta r(n-1)^2) (n-1-n_3(k)) / (n_1(k)-1) \\ g_{\lambda}(k) = (-i(n) + h_i(n)) \Delta i(n-1) / 1E \\ - 2(j \max - j) / j \max (1 - \Delta i(n-1)^2) (n-1-n_3(k)) / (n_1(k)-1)$$

$$\mu(k) = \mu(k) - g_{\mu}(k) \\ \lambda(k) = \lambda(k) - g_{\lambda}(k) \\ (31)$$

in which, the data and fitting correlations of removers and confirmed cases are 0.9998 and 0.9967, respectively.

For the Momentum-SGD algorithm, the cure rate, reinfection rate, and infection rate update formula are as follows:

$$m = 0.1 \\ g_{\mu}(k) = m g_{\mu}(k) \\ + (-r(n) + h_r(n)) \Delta r(n-1) / 1E1(j \max - j) \\ / j \max (1 - \Delta r(n-1)^2) (n-1-n_3(k)) / (n_1(k)-1)$$

$$g_{\lambda}(k) = mg_{\lambda}(k) + (-i(n) + h_i(n))\Delta i1(n-1)/1E$$

$$- 2(j \max - j)/j \max(1 - \Delta i(n-1)^2)(n-1-n3(k))/(n1(k)-1)$$

$$\mu(k) = \mu(k) - g_{\mu}(k)$$

$$\lambda(k) = \lambda(k) - g_{\lambda}(k)$$

(32)

in which, the data and fit correlations for removers and confirmed patients are 0.9998 and 0.9969, respectively.

or the AdaGrad algorithm, the cure rate, reinfection rate, and infection rate update formula are as follows

$$g_{\mu}(k) = (-r(n) + h_r(n))\Delta r(n-1)(1 - \Delta r(n-1)^2)(n-1-n3(k))/(n1(k)-1)$$

$$g_{\lambda}(k) = (-i(n) + h_i(n))\Delta i1(n-1)(1 - \Delta i(n-1)^2)(n-1-n3(k))/(n1(k)-1)$$

$$v(k)_{\mu} = v(k)_{\mu} + g_{\mu}(k)^2$$

$$v(k)_{\lambda} = v(k)_{\lambda} + g_{\lambda}(k)^2$$

$$\mu(k) = \mu(k) - g_{\mu}(k)/\sqrt{v(k)_{\mu}+1e-10/1E4(j \max - j)/j \max}$$

$$\lambda(k) = \lambda(k) - g_{\lambda}(k)/\sqrt{v(k)_{\lambda}+1e-10/1E3(j \max - j)/j \max}$$

(33)

in which, the data and fit correlations for removers and confirmed patients are 0.9972 and 0.9978, respectively.

For the AdaDelta algorithm, the cure rate, reinfection rate, and infection rate update formula are as follows

$$m = 0.1$$

$$beta_1 = 0.999$$

$$g_{\mu}(k) = mg_{\mu}(k)$$

$$+ (-r(n) + h_r(n))\Delta r(n-1)(1 - \Delta r(n-1)^2)(n-1-n3(k))/(n1(k)-1)$$

$$g_{\lambda}(k) = mg_{\lambda}(k)$$

$$+ (-i(n) + h_i(n))\Delta i1(n-1)(1 - \Delta i(n-1)^2)(n-1-n3(k))/(n1(k)-1)$$

$$v(k)_{\mu} = beta_1 v(k)_{\mu} + g_{\mu}(k)^2$$

$$\begin{aligned}
v(k)_\lambda &= \text{beta}_1 v(k)_\lambda + g_\lambda(k)^2 \\
\mu(k) &= \mu(k) - g_\mu(k) / \sqrt{v(k)_\mu + 1e-10/1E4(j \text{ max} - j)/j \text{ max}} \\
\lambda(k) &= \lambda(k) - g_\lambda(k) / \sqrt{v(k)_\gamma + 1e-10/1E3(j \text{ max} - j)/j \text{ max}} \\
(34)
\end{aligned}$$

in which, the data and fit correlations for removers and confirmed patients are 0.9999 and 0.9977, respectively.

For the Adax algorithm, the cure rate, reinfection rate, and infection rate update formula are as follows

$$\begin{aligned}
m_\mu &= 0.1 \\
m_\lambda &= 0.1 \\
m_\alpha &= 0.1 \\
\text{beta}_1 &= 0.9 \\
\text{beta}_2 &= 0.0001 \\
g_\mu(k) &= m g_\mu(k) \\
&\quad + (-r(n) + h_r(n)) \Delta r(n-1) (1 - \Delta r(n-1)^2) (n-1-n_3(k)) / (n_1(k)-1) \\
g_\lambda(k) &= m g_\lambda(k) \\
&\quad + (-i(n) + h_i(n)) \Delta i(n-1) (1 - \Delta i(n-1)^2) (n-1-n_3(k)) / (n_1(k)-1) \\
m_\mu &= \text{beta}_1 m_\mu + (1 - \text{beta}_1) g_\mu(k) \\
m_\lambda &= \text{beta}_1 m_\lambda + (1 - \text{beta}_1) g_\lambda(k) \\
v(k)_\mu &= (1 + \text{beta}_2) v(k)_\mu + \text{beta}_2 g_\mu(k)^2 \\
v(k)_\lambda &= (1 + \text{beta}_2) v(k)_\lambda + \text{beta}_2 g_\lambda(k)^2 \\
vg(k)_\mu &= v(k)_\mu / (1 + \text{beta}_2)^{j-1} \\
vg(k)_\lambda &= v(k)_\lambda / (1 + \text{beta}_2)^{j-1} \\
\mu(k) &= \mu(k) - m_\mu / \sqrt{vg(k)_\mu + 1e-10/1E9(j \text{ max} - j)/j \text{ max}} \\
\lambda(k) &= \lambda(k) - m_\lambda / \sqrt{vg(k)_\lambda + 1e-10/1E9(j \text{ max} - j)/j \text{ max}} \\
(35)
\end{aligned}$$

in which, the data and fit correlations for removers and confirmed patients are 0.9565 and 0.9597, respectively.

For the Adam algorithm, the cure rate, reinfection rate, and infection rate update

formula are as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
m_\mu &= 0.1 \\
m_\lambda &= 0.1 \\
m_\alpha &= 0.1 \\
beta_1 &= 0.9 \\
beta_2 &= 0.999 \\
g_\mu(k) &= mg_\mu(k) \\
&\quad + (-r(n) + h_r(n))\Delta r(n-1)(1 - \Delta r(n-1)^2)(n-1-n3(k))/(n1(k)-1) \\
g_\lambda(k) &= mg_\lambda(k) \\
&\quad + (-i(n) + h_i(n))\Delta i(n-1)(1 - \Delta i(n-1)^2)(n-1-n3(k))/(n1(k)-1) \\
m_\mu &= beta_1 m_\mu + (1 - beta_1)g_\mu(k) \\
m_\lambda &= beta_1 m_\lambda + (1 - beta_1)g_\lambda(k) \\
v(k)_\mu &= beta_2 v(k)_\mu + (1 - beta_2)g_\mu(k)^2 \\
v(k)_\lambda &= beta_2 v(k)_\lambda + (1 - beta_2)g_\lambda(k)^2 \\
vg(k)_\mu &= v(k)_\mu / (1 - beta_2^j) \\
vg(k)_\lambda &= v(k)_\lambda / (1 - beta_2^j) \\
mg(k)_\mu &= m_\mu / (1 - beta_1^j) \\
mg(k)_\lambda &= m_\lambda / (1 - beta_1^j) \\
\mu(k) &= \mu(k) - mg(k)_\mu / \sqrt{vg(k)_\mu + 1e-10/1E8(j \max - j)/jmax} \\
\lambda(k) &= \lambda(k) - mg(k)_\lambda / \sqrt{vg(k)_\lambda + 1e-10/1E10(j \max - j)/jmax}。
\end{aligned}$$

(36)

The data of the remover and the confirmed person are matched. The data and fit the correlations of removers and confirmed cases are 0.9682 and 0.9651, respectively.

The follow-up results are shown in Figure 5.

BGD

SGD

Momentum-SGD

AdaGrad

AdaDelta

Adax

Adam

Figure 5 Deep learning simulation of SEIR model

The follow-up results are shown in Figure 6.

BGD

SGD

Momentum-SGD

AdaGrad

AdaDelta

Adax

Adam

Figure 6 Deep learning simulation of SIR model

Conclusion

The NCIP can even suppress the health care capacity of countries with abundant medical resources, according to experience from China, Italy, and the United States. Besides, in the absence of specific drugs and vaccines, interventions focused on contact tracing, isolation, and social isolation. This has brought great trouble to global public health security and economic development. In this paper, the HIT model of cure rate and infection rate formula is proposed, in which the data of Wuhan is selected to simulate the epidemic situation with SIRS model, the data of Jilin is used to simulate the epidemic situation with SERIS model, the epidemic model is verified with extended Kalman filter tracking data, and the data of Jilin and Wuhan are matched. The innovative meaning of this new model can not only reflect the physical intention, but also achieve the fitting effect of deep understanding. Some key conclusions are obtained as follows.

(1) Due to the lack of latent data and the substitution of suspect data for latent data, the range of α parameter for latent to diagnosed patients has been expanded, and the scope of this parameter has been estimated. The correlation between the actual and the fitting was 0.9984, and the relationship between the real and the joint was 0.9686. Through the analysis of the change of the infection rate, the isolation effect of Jilin Province is reflected on February 2, according to the infection rate.

(2) There are two situations in Wuhan, one is the decrease in infection rate. In this situation, the correlation between the actual and fitted data of Wuhan removed cases was 0.9952, and the relationship between the exact number of confirmed cases and fitted data was 0.9981. The calculation of 67 days City ends. According to the infection rate, the inflection point is February 6. The other is an increase in the rate of infection. In this situation, the correlation between the actual and fitted data of Wuhan migrants was 0.9929, and the relationship between the exact number of confirmed cases and fitted data was 0.9898. The calculation ends at 70 days. 82 days later, we should be alert for the outbreak again. According to the infection rate, the inflection point of the epidemic is to be alert for the second outbreak on March 1.

Appendix

A1 Data of Wuhan

Date	Cumulative discharge	Cumulative death	Residual diagnosis
January 25	8	7	603
January 26	10	25	663
January 27	15	47	1528

January 28	21	66	1818
January 29	28	91	2142
January 30	49	121	2469
January 31	85	154	2976
February 1	117	186	3806
February 2	197	227	4718
February 3	276	275	5833
February 4	341	324	7686
February 5	404	376	9337
February 6	507	440	10671
February 7	671	507	12425
February 8	850	570	13562
February 9	1017	643	15242
February 10	1179	710	16565
February 11	1350	782	17426
February 12	1888	998	30108
February 13	2258	1086	32647
February 14	2744	1193	33977
February 15	3157	1303	35002
February 16	3700	1379	36073
February 17	4461	1451	36840
February 18	5137	1567	37708
February 19	5690	1655	37682
February 20	6456	1754	37136
February 21	7448	1844	36368

February 22	8413	1926	35862
February 23	9185	2057	35307
February 24	10576	2113	34324
February 25	12032	2155	33196
February 26	13567	2174	32025
February 27	16065	2202	29812
February 28	17791	2239	28469
February 29	19466	2265	27333
March 1	21424	2297	25536
March 2	23270	2321	23777
March 3	25129	2352	22001
March 4	26555	2375	20683
March 5	27593	2398	19748

A2 Data of Jilin

Date	Cumulative death	Cumulative discharge	Residual diagnosis	Suspected
January 24	0	4	0	0
January 25	0	4	0	0
January 26	0	6	0	0
January 27	0	8	0	0
January 28	0	9	0	0
January 29	0	14	0	10
January 30	0	13	1	10
January 31	0	16	1	10
February 1	0	22	1	14

February 2	0	30	1	17
February 3	0	41	1	24
February 4	0	53	1	58
February 5	0	57	2	69
February 6	1	61	4	71
February 7	1	65	4	67
February 8	1	73	5	56
February 9	1	68	12	40
February 10	1	68	13	47
February 11	1	65	18	57
February 12	1	62	22	55
February 13	1	61	25	39
February 14	1	63	25	27
February 15	1	61	28	37
February 16	1	59	30	36
February 17	1	55	34	34
February 18	1	54	36	36
February 19	1	51	40	31
February 20	1	47	44	18
February 21	1	45	46	20
February 22	1	39	52	19
February 23	1	39	54	20
February 24	1	33	60	27
February 25	1	30	63	18
February 26	1	28	65	3

February 27	1	25	68	5
February 28	1	20	73	6
February 29	1	18	75	9
March 1	1	15	78	9
March 2	1	10	83	4
March 3	1	9	84	2
March 4	1	7	86	0
March 5	1	5	88	3
March 6	1	3	90	5
March 7	1	3	90	3
March 8	1	3	90	1
March 9	1	2	91	1
March 10	1	2	91	0
March 11	1	2	91	0
March 12	1	2	91	0

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Acknowledgements

Funding. The National Science Foundation of China supports this research under Grant No. 71850013, 71774042, 71271069, and 5207080242; the Special Application Plan for the Construction of National Emergency Management System Grant No. 2020YJ0331030; the National Key R & D Program under Grant No. 2018YFC1504306; the Hunan Innovative Provincial Construction Project under Grant No. 2019RS3009. The co-first author (Ling-Kun Chen) thanks the 2018 Jiangsu Provincial Government Scholarship Program (No. 228) for the support of his visiting at the University of California, Los Angeles.

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Data availability

All the data came from official websites.

Competing interests

The authors declare no competing interest